

The Effects of Job Demands and Job Resources on Subjective Well-Being and Turnover Intention

Mehtap Şeker / Asst. Prof. Dr.

Sivas Cumhuriyet University, Gemerek Vocational School
mehtapseker@cumhuriyet.edu.tr

Mecbure Aslan Teke* / Asst. Prof. Dr.

Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University, Pazarcık Vocational School
mecbureaslan@ksu.edu.tr

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

The target of the study is to determine the effects of job demands and job resources on employees' subjective well-being and their turnover intentions, and to evaluate the implications of these interactions in terms of workplace dynamics. The research was conducted through a survey of 350 participants working in medium-sized businesses in the food sector in the city center of Kayseri. The data in the research were evaluated and the results determined using normality tests, descriptive statistical analyses, confirmatory factor analyses, correlation and regression analyses performed with SPSS 25 and Amos software. The study revealed that job demands and

job resources positively influence employees' subjective well-being and intention to leave. While these results, particularly regarding the positive effect of job demands on subjective well-being and intention to leave, differ from studies in the literature, the positive effect of job resources is similar to other studies. The study also found that subjective well-being negatively affects the intention to leave the job.

Keywords: Job Demands, Job Resources, Subjective Well-being, Turnover Intentions.

JEL Codes: L20, L21, L25

Citation: Şeker, M. & Aslan Teke, M. (2026). The effects of job demands and job resources on subjective well-being and turnover intention. *Researches on Multidisciplinary Approaches (ROMAYA Journal)*, 2026(2).

1. Introduction

Job demands and resources are two fundamental notions that refer to the requirements, challenges, and expectations employees encounter in their working lives, as well as the supportive elements that help them cope with these challenges. Job demands generally encompass organizational aspects of work that increase employees' physical or psychological effort, lead to energy depletion, and are therefore evaluated negatively (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Heavy workload, time pressure, or emotional demands can be given as examples of such demands (Xanthopoulou *vd.*, 2007). In contrast, job resources refer to elements considered beneficial and mitigating the adverse effects of job demands, such as employee motivation, personal development, and advancement (Schaufeli & Taris, 2014). Support from colleagues, feedback from supervisors, autonomy, and supportive leadership can be provided as examples of job resources (Metin, 2010).

Theoretically, it is argued that high job demands increase the risk of stress, burnout, and decreased job satisfaction among employees; conversely, strong job resources counterbalance these negative effects by protecting employees' subjective well-being. Subjective well-being is a subjective assessment, encompassing both cognitive and emotional dimensions, that reflects the extent to which a person perceives their life as meaningful, satisfying, and positive (Diener, 1984, Diener and Diener, 1996). Therefore, subjective well-being is directly related not only to an individual's personal life but also to their experiences in their work life. In this context, in situations where high job demands prevail in work life, providing sufficient levels of supportive job resources is critical for employees to maintain their subjective well-being.

It is known that job demand and resources affect not only the subjective well-being of employees, but also their attitudes towards organizational outcomes. One of the most prominent of these attitudes is turnover intention. According to Schaufeli and Bakker (2004), intention to leave a job refers to an employee's conscious and planned tendency to leave their current organization. In other words, turnover intention involves employees planning to leave their current job or considering alternative employment opportunities without necessarily taking action to quit. In this context, excessively high work demands and insufficient work resources can increase the intention to leave a job (Bon & Shire, 2017). On the other hand, strong work resources both mitigate the negative effects of their demands and play an important role in increasing individual' organizational commitment and motivation, and reducing their intention to leave the job (Schaufeli & Taris, 2014; Bakker, Demerouti, Boer, & Schaufeli, 2003).

In conclusion, job demands and job resources play a decisive role in shaping both employees' subjective well-being and their turnover intentions. Therefore, for organizations, developing strategies that balance job demands and provide sufficient job resources not only helps reduce the anxiety and worry employees face at work and improves their subjective well-being, but also contributes to reducing turnover intention. Accordingly, this research evaluates the variables of subjective well-being, job demands, job resources, and turnover intention, which have been shown in the literature to interact with each other, in terms of their effects on employees and the workplace environment.. Various studies addressing these areas exist in the literature. However, a review of national and international research indicates that job demands and job resources have often been examined in a limited manner, and studies that evaluate these concepts together with subjective well-being and turnover intention within a holistic framework remain scarce. Therefore, this study goals to conduce to the literature by analyzing these variables collectively; to identify the positive and negative impacts of job demands and work resources on employees; and particularly to reveal their implications for employees' subjective well-being and turnover intentions.

2 . Conceptual Framework

2.1. Job Demands and Job Resources

One theoretical approach to explaining the effects of the organizational environment on employee behavior and attitudes, such as employee happiness and job performance, is the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) theory. This theory suggests that the job qualifications of employees in different sectors and various positions can be conceptualized under two main dimensions: job demands and job resources (Tummers & Bakker, 2021).

Job demands are conceptualized as elements that require a certain level of effort or exertion from the employee, as well as a certain level of attention and reaction, within the context of the work environment and the structural characteristics of the job (Jones & Fletcher, 1996). Job demands encompass the efforts employees must demonstrate in performing their jobs, sometimes requiring physical strength, sometimes emotional resilience, and sometimes relational and organizational skills. While these job requirements don't always lead to harmful consequences for the employee, when experienced continuously and intensely, they can become a significant source of stress and cause negative psychological conditions such as burnout, anxiety, and depression among employees (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004).

Cavanaugh et al. (2000), building on the processor theory of stress, categorized job demands into two categories: challenging and hindering requirements, and suggested that coping processes and outcomes vary depending on this category of demand. Demands related to challenging requirements represent stressful situations; however, when successfully managed, they can be beneficial for personal growth and advancement. In contrast, hindrance demands obstruct job performance and hinder personal development and progress. Since Cavanaugh et al. (2000) proposed dividing job demands into two categories: challenging demands and hindering demands, numerous studies have focused on the conceptual and consequences distinction between these demands. For instance, Lin, Oi-ling, Kan, and Xin-wen (2009) provided important insights regarding employee motivation and the effects of workplace stress. According to their findings, employees may experience burnout particularly when job demands are perceived as restrictive, whereas developmental or growth-oriented job demands may be viewed as beneficial for employees. Similarly, Tadić, Bakker, and Oerlemans (2015) addressed job demands within the framework of compulsive and deterrent stressors developed by Le Pine and colleagues (2005). Accordingly, challenge demands like workload and work complicacy require effort and energy; however, when managed effectively, they can contribute to employees' development, ascertain, and achieving the aim. For example, highly complex job responsibilities necessitate a significant transfer of energy while also fostering expertise and experience. Conversely, hindrance demands include job descriptions and conditions that require effort and strength but offer little or no opportunity for competence development (Le Pine et al., 2005; Van den Broeck et al., 2010). In conclusion, it may not be accurate to evaluate job demands solely as negative or harmful. Indeed, Bakker et al. (2007, 2010) argued in their studies that not all job demands may lead to harmful consequences (Tadić et al., 2015).

Work resources consist of structural and social elements of work that support employees in achieving their work goals, mitigate various costs that may arise from work demands, and encourage individual development and professional learning processes (Schaufeli, 2017). These resources may manifest in various forms, including social support, autonomy and control over tasks, performance feedback, opportunities for development, and engagement in meaningful work. For instance, support from colleagues or supervisors can enable employees to cope more effectively with workplace challenges; control over one's work may help employees manage job demands more efficiently; and structured performance feedback can enhance motivation by fostering individual learning processes and professional development (Schaufeli, 2017).

Job demands and job resources, which reflect specific aspects or characteristics of work in every occupation, are important because they initiate two distinct processes within the work environment (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014). Essentially, this framework integrates two psychological processes. The first is the stressful process involving health problems or strain, such as burnout, caused by excessive work demands and insufficient work resources. The second is a more desirable and motivating process triggered by abundant work resources, such as organizational commitment and the desire to remain in the workplace (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004; Schaufeli, 2017). Accordingly, workplace demands and job-related resources create a holistic model that generates different processes and effects. In this context, the third proposition of the JD-R theory is that both together affect occupational well-being. This combined effect is reflected in workplace performance in two ways: initially, job-related resources alleviate the stress caused by job demands; finally, job demands reinforce the motivation and commitment supported by job resources (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014).

In conclusion, the JD-R theory demonstrates that there is a reciprocal interaction among the structural characteristics of work and employees' well-being and motivation. The theory explains that work demands and work resources in the workplace do not produce only positive outcomes; it also clarifies the mechanisms through which negative effects may emerge. In this context, it presents a framework that emphasizes the need to reorganize job characteristics from the employees' perspective and design the work environment in a way that makes it less tiring for employees (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014). In essence, the theory highlights the importance of simultaneously reducing job demands while increasing job resources (Schaufeli, 2017).

2.2. Subjective Well-Being

Subjective well-being is a concept composed of individuals' perceptions or evaluations of their lives and is commonly referred to as happiness in everyday language. These perceptions primarily involve a cognitive dimension, encompassing evaluative judgments such as life satisfaction. In addition, subjective well-being includes an affective dimension, manifested through pleasant and unpleasant emotional responses (Diener & Diener, 1996). In this context, subjective well-being at the cognitive level is shaped by an individual's increasing satisfaction in different areas like their work life, family life, and personal life; while at the emotional level, it is related to the person having positive feelings and thoughts about their life when life events are evaluated positively (Myers & Diener, 1995).

According to Diener (1984), subjective well-being has three fundamental characteristics. First, it is ba-

sed on a subjective evaluation; thus, the essence of well-being lies in individuals' personal judgments regarding the quality and nature of their own lives. Second, subjective well-being emphasizes positive criteria or indicators rather than solely focusing on negative aspects. Third, the dimensions of subjective well-being encompass a global assessment of all aspects of an individual's life. Owing to this characteristic, subjective well-being not only allows for the assessment of affect or satisfaction within specific life domains but also highlights a holistic evaluation of one's overall life experience.

A person's happiness in life and high levels of subjective well-being significantly improve the individual's circumstances in four key areas: well-being and lifespan, employment and earnings, interpersonal connections and community involvement (Gencer, 2018). In this context, high subjective well-being reflects the predominance of positive thoughts and emotional states regarding one's life. On the other hand, individuals with low levels of subjective well-being tend to evaluate their life circumstances and experiences negatively, and are more susceptible to experiencing negative emotions such as anxiety about the future, depressive mood, and anger (Myers & Diener, 1995).

The primary aim of scholars examining subjective well-being extends beyond merely eliminating distress; it also involves promoting the organization and improvement of individuals' lives. As subjective well-being constitutes a significant component of quality of life, its measurement is crucial for understanding how individuals' lives can become more fulfilling and meaningful. Furthermore, numerous studies have demonstrated that high levels of subjective well-being not only provide advantages at the individual level but also contribute to the effective functioning of societies (Gencer, 2018). For example, various studies have explored the relationships between subjective well-being and variables such as age, gender, physical health, economic status, genetic characteristics, marital status, and personality. Among these, the studies conducted by Diener et al. (1999), Myers and Diener (1995), and Lykken and Tellegen (1996) are particularly noteworthy.

2.3. Turnover Intention

Psychological studies indicate that individuals' intentions are often significant predictors of their behaviors. From this perspective, Kristensen and Westergård-Nielsen (2004) suggest that job-seeking behavior is in fact a significant reflection of a person's act of leaving their job. (Böckermann & Ilmakunnas, 2004). Accordingly, turnover intention can be defined as an individual's behavioral attitude toward withdrawal from the workplace, whereas turnover refers to the actual act of leaving the organization (Aydoğdu & Işıkçıl, 2011).

According to Sutherland and Wilhelm (2004: 56), turnover intention can be classified as voluntary or involuntary. They define voluntary turnover intention as an action initiated by employees due to expectations of a better employment environment or dissatisfaction with their current job. In contrast, involuntary turnover intention is described as termination initiated by the employer for reasons unrelated to employee misconduct or performance.

Turnover intention can be classified into three categories: unavoidable, desirable, and undesirable turnover intention. Unavoidable turnover intention arises from circumstances such as family-related reasons, personal illness, or retirement. Desirable turnover intention occurs due to employee inadequacy. In contrast, undesirable turnover intention refers to the departure of skilled and well-trained employees as a result of organizational problems such as insufficient support, role conflict, and lack of supervision (Rizvan, Arshad, Munir, Iqbal, & Hussain, 2014).

Studies examining the reasons why employees leave their jobs are found not only in research focusing on job and organizational characteristics such as job and organizational design and job stress, but also in literature where human resources are important and their management is addressed. Studies on job and organizational design have shown that job demands; various stress factors; and conditions such as task repetition and routinization are positively correlated with turnover. For example, Almalki et al. (2012) found meaningful relationships between turnover intention and demographic variables.

Turnover intention is defined as a cognitive process that includes thinking about leaving, planning to leave, and the desire to quit; it may also result in an intention to stay, depending on employees' levels of loyalty and commitment to their organizations. Therefore, various other factors may influence individuals' intention to remain within an organization (Vigneshwaran & Mohankumar, 2022). Employees exposed to unfavorable working conditions tend to have higher intentions to change jobs. For instance, employees who face uncertainty, work in mentally demanding roles, believe that there are no opportunities for promotion, or experience discrimination are more likely to be willing to leave their jobs (Böckermann & Ilmakunnas, 2004).

Vigneshwaran and Mohankumar (2022) explain various antecedents affecting employees' intentions to leave their jobs in terms of conflict between family and work, work and general life balance. From their perspective, factors such as work stress, work satisfaction, demographic variables (e.g., monthly income, etc.), opportunities for responsibility and autonomy in developing one's own work activities, organizational identity, and a sense of commitment, such as dedication to the job, are considered antecedents of turnover intention. An example of research in this

area is the study conducted by Ahmad, Bashir and colleagues (2012). The results of their research show that work satisfaction and work stress are significantly and negatively correlated with turnover intention. Accordingly, as levels of job stress increase, employees' intention to leave the job also increases.

In another study, Galetta, Portoghese, and Battistelli (2011) showed that providing individuals with more responsibility and autonomy in their work can improve feelings of identification and commitment in the workplace, thereby reducing turnover intention. The study emphasized the importance of intrinsic motivation in promoting affective commitment and found that affective commitment fully mediated the relationship between intrinsic motivation and turnover intention. In this context, the findings have shown that the higher individuals' intrinsic motivation towards their jobs, the more likely they are to develop a sense of integration and commitment to their organizations, and this negatively affects their intention to leave the job.

Randhawa (2007) examined turnover intention and reported significant correlations between turnover intention and demographic variables such as age, qualifications, and job title. The study showed that age, title, and competency were meaning and negatively associated with turnover intention, and that an employee's intention to leave an organization was largely influenced by their age, title, and experience. The negative relationships identified in the study suggest that as age, experience, and organizational status increase, turnover intentions decrease significantly.

2.4. The Relationship Between Job Demands, Job Resources, and Subjective Well-Being

When examining the connection among work characteristics and individuals' subjective well-being in the context of job demands and resources related to job requirements, responsibilities, and the nature of the work, studies conducted across different occupational groups show that the JD-R model has a significant impact on employees' capacity to experience their lives with positive or negative emotions. For instance, a study conducted by Claees, Vandepitte, Clays, and Annemans (2023) found that job demands and job resources are directly related to subjective well-being. While job resources show a positive correlation with subjective well-being, job demands show a negative correlation. Moreover, job resources appear to have a stronger relationship with subjective well-being compared to job demands. Job satisfaction mediates these relationships, indirectly contributing to employees' subjective well-being. The findings reveal that improving work resources has a significant impact on increasing employees'

subjective well-being.

In another study examining the effects of job characteristics on subjective well-being, JD-R model was employed to assess the relative importance of job characteristics in relation to the subjective well-being of teachers in the United Kingdom. The findings revealed that teachers demonstrated higher levels of subjective well-being when work-life conflict decreased. Furthermore, various job resources were found to mitigate the negative effects of job demands. Another research investigating work demands and work resources explored the subjective well-being of accountants and assessed the mediating role of job resources in the link between work demands and subjective well-being. Within the accounting field, various work demands that adversely influence subjective well-being tend to build up over time. In contrast, work resources were found to exert a positive effect on subjective well-being (Ostermeier, Koops, & Peccei, 2023).

Another study addressing job demands and job resources examined the subjective well-being of accountants and analyzed the mediating effect of job resources on the relationship between job demands and subjective well-being. In the accounting profession, various job demands that negatively affect subjective well-being tend to accumulate. In contrast to the effects of job demands, job resources were found to have a positive impact on subjective well-being. The study also revealed that job demands and job resources directly influence subjective well-being without mediation. Moreover, it was determined that work resources (such as task autonomy and social support) serve as a mediator in the association between subjective well-being and work demands (both quantitative and qualitative), and that when professionals in this field encounter the highest intensity of work demands, they are likely to perceive themselves as having fewer resources available to manage those demands (Molina-Sánchez et al., 2019).

In addition to these investigations, Han, Yin, and Wang (2020) and Zhao, Yuan, and Hu (2024) also explored the association between work demands, work resources, and subjective well-being. Han et al. (2020) reported that work demands have a detrimental effect on the subjective well-being of academic personnel, whereas work resources positively influence their subjective well-being. Likewise, Zhao et al. (2024) found that teaching load is negatively related to subjective well-being and that the harmful impact of work demands primarily arises from teaching-related duties. Overall, these empirical findings are consistent with the JD-R model; however, it is also stated that the relationships between job characteristics and employee well-being are not solely unidirectional and may develop reciprocally over time (Lesener et al., 2019).

2.5. The Relationship Between Job Demands and Job Resources and Turnover Intentions

There are two lines of research that examine the relationships between work demands and turnover intention, and between work resources and turnover intention. The first pertains to the literature on job and organizational design as well as occupational stress, which emphasizes work and organizational factors that may prompt employees to leave their positions. The second relates to the human resource management literature, which highlights practices that help organizations achieve their strategic objectives by attracting, retaining, and efficiently managing personnel. Both perspectives are significant within the JD–R model framework. While the job design and occupational stress literature primarily concentrates on work demands, the human resource management literature emphasizes work resources (Hoonakker et al., 2013).

There are empirical studies examining the direct effects of individual characteristics, working conditions, and job attributes on employees' likelihood of leaving their jobs and their tenure. For example, unfavorable working conditions have been shown to increase turnover intention (Böckermann & Ilmakunnas, 2004). The JD–R model assumes that two sets of working conditions—namely demands and resources—can each trigger different processes. High job demands are likely to lead to strain reactions (e.g., stress, burnout), which may result in increased absenteeism and turnover. On the other hand, resources (e.g., decision latitude, social support) are more likely to promote goal achievement, leading to positive work attitudes and reduced turnover intention. Job resources refer to the physical, psychological, social, and organizational aspects of a job that are effective in achieving work goals, reducing job demands and their associated costs, and promoting learning. In this context, job resources are not only functional in attaining work objectives but also foster personal growth and development (Hoonakker et al., 2013).

Hoonakker and colleague (2013) investigated the association between work demands, work resources, and turnover intention within the JD–R model framework, emphasizing gender-based differences in these relationships. Their results suggest that emotional exhaustion serves as a mediator between work demands and turnover intention, while job satisfaction mediates the link between work resources and turnover intention. Furthermore, significant gender differences were identified within these associations.

High employee turnover intentions have always been a significant concern for the telecommunications sector. This issue is particularly pronounced among employees in developing countries, where turnover

intentions are notably high (Bon & Shire, 2017). Bon and Shire (2017) showed in their study that employees facing high job demands are more likely to intend to leave their jobs. Indeed, this result reveals a link between job demands and employees' intentions to leave their jobs. Within the framework of the JD–R model, workload—considered one of the employees' job demands—was investigated by Jasiński and Derbis (2022), who found that workload is the strongest direct predictor of the intention to leave one's current job or profession. Organizational constraints and interpersonal conflicts in the workplace trigger negative experiences, which in turn lead to turnover intentions. Among these factors, interpersonal conflicts at work are the strongest predictors of negative emotions in the workplace. The findings of this study indicate that workload directly influences both types of turnover intentions, while organizational constraints and interpersonal conflicts indirectly increase intentions to leave the job or profession by eliciting negative affect at work.

Other studies examining turnover intention include those by Mansour and Azeem (2024) and Galetta et al. (2011). Galetta and colleagues (2011) reported that granting employees responsibility and autonomy in managing their work tasks can enhance their sense of identification with and commitment to the workplace, which in turn decreases turnover intention. They suggest that when employees are intrinsically motivated toward their work, they cultivate a sense of organizational identification and attachment, which is inversely related to their intention to leave the organization. Mansour and Azeem (2024), in contrast, examined the impact of work–family conflict, emotional exhaustion, and elevated job demands on flight attendants' turnover intentions. Their results indicated a positive association between heightened job demands and the intention to leave. Hoare & Vandenberghe (2024) state in their study that employee well-being is more strongly influenced by job demands, while job resources, although also supporting well-being, play a particularly stronger role in reducing turnover intentions. These findings emphasize that both job demands and resources affect employees' subjective well-being and also play an important role in shaping their intentions to stay with or leave the organization. Therefore, turnover intention is considered one of the key outcomes of the job demands–resources model.

3. Research Method

A quantitative research method was adopted in the study. Data were collected using a survey technique from employees working in food sector enterprises located in the city center of Kayseri.

In this study, food sector businesses operating in Kayseri province were selected, taking into account cost and accessibility factors in the data collection process. The fact that the food sector combines high

The Effects of Job Demands and Job Resources on Subjective Well-Being and Turnover Intention

job demands and significant job resources provides a context consistent with the theoretical framework of the research, as it offers a work environment that can affect employees' subjective well-being and turnover intentions. Furthermore, the accessibility of

Kayseri province for the researcher and the reduction of data collection costs increased the feasibility of the study. Accordingly, considering both theoretical suitability and practical limitations, the Kayseri food sector was determined as the research sample.

Figure 1. Developed Research Model

The hypotheses developed within the framework of this research model are as follows:

H1a: Workload, as a job demand, negatively affects employees' levels of subjective well-being.

H1b: Emotional demands, as a job demand, negatively affect employees' levels of subjective well-being.

H1c: Emotional dissonance, as a job demand, negatively affects employees' levels of subjective well-being.

H1d: Changes at Work, one of the job demand, negatively affect employees' levels of subjective well-being.

H2a: Autonomy, as a job resource, positively affects employees' levels of subjective well-being.

H2b: Colleague support, as a job resource, positively affects employees' levels of subjective well-being.

H2c: Coaching, as a job resource, positively affects employees' levels of subjective well-being.

H2d: Personal development, as a job resource, positively affects employees' levels of subjective well-being.

H3a: Workload, one of the job demand, positively affects employees' turnover intention.

H3b: Emotional demands, one of the job demand, positively affect employees' turnover intention.

H3c: Emotional dissonance, one of the job demand, positively affects employees' turnover intention.

H3d: Changes at Work, one of the job demand, positively affect employees' turnover intention.

H4a: Autonomy, one of the job resources negatively affects employees' turnover intention.

H4b: Colleague support, one of the job resource, negatively affects employees' turnover intention.

H4c: Coaching, one of the job resource, negatively affects employees' turnover intention.

H4d: Personal development, one of the job resource, negatively affects employees' turnover intention.

H5: Subjective well-being negatively affect turnover intention.

4. Study Sample

The study's population compose of 7,086 workers employed in the food sector in Kayseri (SGK, 2024). The sample comprises 350 employees working in these businesses in Kayseri. Data were collected through both face-to-face and online surveys. In studies where the population size is 20,000, a sample size of 318 is considered sufficient (Bayram, 2004: 10). Furthermore, Hair, Black, Tatham, and Anderson (2010) suggest that a sample size five times larger than the number of survey items is considered good and sufficient. The measurement instrument used in this study consists of a total of 68 items: 29 items for the subjective well-being scale, 3 items for turnover intention, and 36 items for job demands and resources. Therefore, a sample of 350 participants is considered more than sufficient. Approval for the study has been obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Social and Human Sciences at Sivas Cumhuriyet University (No: E-99711239-050-04-518679, Date: 21.01.2025).

5. Data Collection Instruments

The study utilized scales for job demands and job resources, a turnover intention scale, and a subjective well-being scale. Accordingly:

Subjective Well-Being Scale: To determine emp-

loyees' levels of subjective well-being, the 29-item Oxford Happiness Inventory (Hills & Argyle, 2002) was utilized. The survey items were presented with response options ranging from (1) Strongly Disagree to (5) Strongly Agree to assess the level of subjective well-being. The Turkish adaptation of the scale was obtained from the study by Yurcu and Atay (2015). The validity of the scale is considered acceptable, as indicated by values like RMSEA: 0.82, CFI: 0.94, and χ^2/df : 4.2, as reported in Doğan and Sapmaz (2012: 302).

Turnover Intention Scale: To measure employees' intention to leave their jobs, the scale developed by Cammann et al. (1979) and used in Gülertekin's (2013) study was utilized. Questions were evaluated on a Likert-type scale answered with, for example, (1) Strongly Disagree (Gülertekin, 2013). This three-item scale, adapted from the Michigan Organizational Assessment Questionnaire, was found to be reliable, with a reliability coefficient of 0.88 based on reliability and validity analyses (Yapıcı, 2008: 118).

Job Demands and Resources Scale: The scale developed by Xanthopoulou et al. (2007) and used in Metin's (2010) study was used to assess what the job-related demands and resources are in the workplace. Items were rated on a scale ranging from (1) Never to (5) Always. The job demands dimension includes four sub-dimensions: workload, emotional deman-

ds, emotional dissonance, and changes at work. The job resources dimension consists of four sub-dimensions: automation, colleague support, coaching, and personal development (Metin, 2010).

6. Findings

Participants' demographic characteristics were analyzed through frequency analysis. Regarding gender composition, 35% of the respondents were female and 65% were male. The age distribution was as follows: 1.3% were between 16–20 years old, 13.4% between 21–30, 38.6% between 31–40, 40.5% between 41–50, and 6.2% between 51–60. In terms of marital status, 68.3% of the participants were married, whereas 31.7% were single.

With respect to educational attainment, 9.5% had completed high school, 23.2% held an associate degree, 52.3% possessed a bachelor's degree, 13.4% had a master's degree, and 1.6% had earned a doctoral degree. Concerning organizational tenure, 19.9% had worked at the company for 1–5 years, 43.8% for 6–10 years, 30.1% for 11–15 years, and 6.2% for 16 years or more.

The relationships between the scales were examined using correlation analysis and are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Correlation Results of Research Variables

	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	9	10	11	12
Turnover Intention	1										
Subjective Well-being	-,211**	1									
Workload	-,098	,478**	1								
Emotional Demands	-,128**	,501**	,720**	1							
Emotional Dissonance	-,133**	,531**	,743**	,895**	1						
Changes at Work	-,149**	,510**	,680**	,851**	,840**	1					
Job Demands	-,143**	,547**	,817**	,952**	,945**	,940**	1				
Autonomy	-,239**	,570**	,436**	,439**	,450**	,508**	,504**	1			
Colleague Support	-,286**	,570**	,481**	,418**	,436**	,484**	,494**	,819**	1		
Coaching	-,288**	,613**	,473**	,438**	,459**	,454**	,492**	,829**	,885**	1	
Personal Development	-,243**	,587**	,473**	,396**	,411**	,432**	,460**	,826**	,870**	,912**	1
Job Resources	-,282**	,622**	,492**	,448**	,466**	,493**	,515**	,911**	,941**	,970**	,953**

**p<0,01

According to Table 1, job demands, job resources, and their sub-dimensions are negatively correlated with turnover intention (**p<0.01: -0.143; -0.282**), while job demands, job resources, and their sub-dimensions are positively correlated with subjective well-being (**p<0.01: 0.547; 0.622**). In other words, as job demands and resources decrease, the turnover intention the job decreases, while as job demands and resources increase, subjective well-being levels also increase. The study also observed an inverse relationship between subjective well-being and turnover intention (**p<0.01: -0.211**).

6.1. Validity and Reliability Analyses of the Scales, Normal Distribution and Mean of the Data

As a result of the analysis, the following index values were examined for the scales: $\chi^2/sd < 5$, RMSEA, TLI value, and some other index values. A model is considered to have a good fit if

its $\chi^2/sd < 5$ is less than 5 and its CFI and TLI values are 0.90 or higher (Schermele-Engel, Moosbrugger & Müller, 2003).

Table 2. Calculated Fit Indices for the Scales

Acceptable Compliance Indexes	Turnover Intentions	Subjective Well-being	Job Demands and Job Resources
$\chi^2/sd < 5$	2,151	3,645	2,367
GFI >0.90	0,951	0,936	0,952
AGFI >0.90	0,916	0,921	0,912
CFI >0.90	0,921	0,912	0,905
TLI >0.90	0,907	0,917	0,936
RMSEA <0.08	0,076	0,079	0,066

Source: Hu & Bentler (1999); Kline (2016).

When the fit indices were examined, it was determined that the measurement models showed a good level of fit with the data. These findings indicate that the factor structures of the scales were validated and that they reliably measured the relevant constructs. To determine the reliability levels of the scales, a

reliability analysis was conducted and Cronbach's alpha coefficients were examined. Accordingly, the values determined for turnover intention were 0.931, for subjective well-being 0.844, and for job demands and job resources 0.766, indicating that the scales are reliable.

Table 3. Standard Deviation, Variance, Mean, Skewness and Kurtosis Values of the Data

	TI	SW	JD	JD_W	JD_EDE	JD_EDİ	JD_CW	JR	JR_A	JR_PS	JR_C	JR_PD
Mean	2,2440	3,2958	3,3449	3,4003	3,3361	3,3817	3,2946	3,3915	3,2767	3,3867	3,4118	3,4771
Standard Deviation	1,02537	,75073	,92269	,97230	1,00703	,96872	1,01444	,97208	1,02876	1,01018	1,02230	1,04386
Variance	1,051	,564	,851	,945	1,014	,938	1,029	,945	1,058	1,020	1,045	1,090
Skewness	1,203	-,417	-,483	-,363	-,468	-,462	-,502	-,518	-,386	-,480	-,476	-,538
Kurtosis	,518	-,772	-1,028	-,839	-,819	-,779	-,874	-,819	-,818	-,748	-,809	-,749

In this study, the data shows a normal distribution, meaning that the kurtosis and skewness values, mean, and frequency values indicate that the data are normally distributed. As reported in the literature, skewness and kurtosis coefficients within the range of ± 1.5 are considered indicative of normal distribution. According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2015), values falling among -1.5 and $+1.5$ suggest that the data exhibit a normal distribution. In Table 3, the mean for turnover intention variable was found to be 2.2440, the mean for the subjective well-being vari-

able was 3.2958, the mean for the job demands variable was 3.3449, and the mean for the job resources variable was 3.3915.

6.2. Results of Regression Analyses of Variables

The regression analysis results and data of the variables in the study, conducted within the framework of the hypotheses formulated, are given in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4. The Effect of Job Demands, Job Resources on Subjective Well-being

Independent Variables	B	S.D.	p	R	R2	Adj. R2	F	t	DW
Job Demands	,450	,039	,000	,553	,306	,304	134,081	11,579	1,765
Workload	,380	,030	,000	,492	,242	,239	96,882	9,843	1,802
Emotional Demands	,377	,037	,000	,505	,255	,253	10,206	104,162	1,807
Emotional Dissonance	,416	,038	,000	,536	,288	,285	122,707	11,077	1,835
Changes at Work	,382	,036	,000	,517	,267	,264	110,663	10,520	1,708
Job resources	,479	,035	,000	,620	,384	,382	189,798	13,777	1,733
Autonomy	,416	,034	,000	,570	,324	,322	146,036	12,085	1,737
Colleague Support	,423	,035	,000	,570	,325	,322	146,167	12,090	1,802
Coaching	,449	,033	,000	,611	,374	,372	181,440	13,470	1,730
Personal Development	,420	,033	,000	,584	,340	,338	156,944	12,528	1,753

Dependent Variable: Subjective Well-being

Based on the findings of the regression analyses, as presented in Table 4, job demands and their sub-dimensions—workload, emotional demands, emotional dissonance, and changes at work—positively affect subjective well-being. Accordingly, an increase in job demands increases the level of subjective well-being. In this case, hypotheses H1a, H1b, H1c, and H1d, which predicted a negative effect, were rejected. On the other hand, job resources and their

sub-dimensions, such as automation, colleague support, coaching, and personal development, have a positive effect on subjective well-being, and as job resources increase, the level of subjective well-being also increases (B = 0.479, p < 0.01). The job resources dimension explains 38% of an individual's subjective well-being (R² = 0.384). Based on these results, hypotheses H2a, H2b, H2c, and H2d are confirmed.

Table 5. The Effect of Job Demands, Resources, Subjective Well-being on Turnover Intentions

Independent Variables	B	S.D.	p	R	R2	Adj. R2	F	t	DW
Job Demands	-,159	,063	,012	,143	,021	,017	6,377	-2,525	1,904
Workload	-,117	,060	,053	,111	,012	,009	3,767	-1,941	1,896
Emotional Demands	-,131	,058	,025	,128	,016	,013	5,079	-2,254	1,911
Emotional Dissonance	-,141	,060	,020	,133	,018	,014	5,476	-2,340	1,891
Changes at Work	-,151	,057	,009	,149	,022	,019	6,934	-2,633	1,927
Job resources	-,297	,058	,000	,282	,079	,076	26,232	-5,122	1,945
Autonomy	-,239	,056	,000	,239	,057	,054	18,467	-4,297	1,939
Colleague Support	-,290	,056	,000	,286	,082	,079	29,986	-5,195	1,966

Coaching	-,289	,055	,000	,288	,083	,080	27,496	-5,244	1,934
Personal Development	-,238	,055	,000	,243	,059	,056	19,002	-4,359	1,941
Subjective Well-being	-,288	,077	,000	,211	,045	,041	14,177	-3,765	1,866

Dependent Variable: Turnover Intention

Based on the findings of the regression analyses, as presented Table 5, job demands and their sub-dimensions, namely emotional demands, emotional dissonance and changes at work, negatively affect turnover intention ($B = -0.159, p < 0.01$). The job demands dimension explains 2.1% of an individual's turnover intention ($R^2 = 0.021$). Accordingly, an increase in job demands reduces turnover intention. In this case, hypothesis H3, which predicts a positive effect, is rejected in the study. On the other hand, all job resources and their sub-dimensions negatively affect turnover intention, with turnover intention decreasing as job resources increase ($B = -0.297, p < 0.01$). The job resources dimension explains 7.9% of an individual's turnover intention ($R^2 = 0.079$). Based on these results, hypotheses H4a, H4b, H4c, and H4d are confirmed, while hypotheses H3a, H3b, H3c, and H3d are rejected due to the presence of a negative effect.

As also shown in Table 5, subjective well-being negatively affects turnover intention ($B = -0.288, p < 0.01$). The level of subjective well-being explains 21% of the variation in an individual's turnover intention ($R^2 = 0.211$). This finding shows that as the level of subjective well-being increases, turnover intention decreases, and confirms hypothesis H5.

7. Discussion

Following the correlation and regression examinations, it was determined that among the subdimensions of job demands, workload, emotional demands, emotional dissonance, and changes in the workplace exerted a beneficial effect on the level of subjective well-being. This finding indicates that an increase in job demands may enhance the level of subjective well-being; however, this outcome is not consistent with other studies in the literature. For example, different findings were reported in the studies conducted by Han and co-authors (2020), Zhao and co-authors (2024), Molina-Sánchez and co-authors (2019), Claees and co-authors (2023), and Ostermeier et al. (2023), Dishon-Berkovits, M. et al (2024), Pulido-Martos, M., et al. (2023) and Jin, M., et al. (2025).

According to the research findings, emotional demands evaluated within the scope of job requirements, emotional dissonance, and workplace changes outside of workload were found to have a negative impact on the intention to leave the job. However, these findings do not align with studies

in the existing literature (e.g., Hoonakker and colleagues, 2013; Bon & Shire, 2017; Jasiński & Derbis, 2022). The findings that differ from the literature may be attributed to variables such as the socio-economic structure of our country, as well as cultural, sectoral, psychological, and individual differences. Therefore, these aspects of the job demands variable could be addressed by other researchers to shed light on alternative evaluations. Another possible reason for this discrepancy can be explained by the impact of job resources on job demands. The literature frequently emphasizes that job resources play a critical role in mitigating the negative consequences of job demands faced by employees. Jin et al. (2016) demonstrate that person–organization fit can function as a protective organizational resource for employees. In this regard, it is suggested that high levels of person–organization fit may reduce the negative impact of job demands and perceived threats on employees' turnover intentions. Moreover, this difference can be evaluated within the framework of challenge demands and hindrance demands as explained by Cavanaugh and colleagues (2000). Tadić and colleagues (2014) argue that difficult demands, like workload and occupational intricacy, although requiring effort, facilitate learning and goal achievement when their adverse aspects are effectively managed. In this situation, complicated work assignments demand substantial amounts of energy but may also promote employees' growth in expertise and proficiency. In conclusion, based on the work of Bakker et al. (2007, 2010), it can be argued that, given that not all job demands are inherently harmful, these demands may also have a positive effect on employees' turnover intentions.

The first finding of the study regarding job resources is that job resources like autonomy, colleague support, coaching, and personal development positively affect employees' levels of subjective well-being. These findings are in line with those documented in the literature by Han and colleagues (2020), Zhao and colleagues (2024), Molina-Sánchez and colleagues (2019), Claees and colleagues (2023), and Ostermeier and colleagues (2023). The second finding related to job resources is that subdimensions such as automation, coworker support, coaching, and personal development have a negative effect on turnover intention. This result is consistent with other studies in the literature, such as those by Galetta and colleagues (2011), Hoonakker and col-

leagues (2013), and Bon and Shire (2017). As seen, most job demands and job resources variables are associated with and have an impact on employees' intention to leave their jobs. For instance, studies conducted by Moloney, W. et al. (2018), Eriksson, A. et al. (2021), and Montecinos, C. et al. (2026) examined these relationships and effects. In addition, Leep-Lazar, K. et al. (2026) supported a model proposing that high job demands and insufficient job resources negatively affect mental health and increase employees' intention to leave their jobs.

In conclusion, the findings of this study reveal that increased job demands and job-related resources reduce employees' intentions to leave their jobs. Additionally, it was observed that increases in job resources and job demands were also associated with higher levels of employees' subjective well-being. This indicates that both employees' commitment to their jobs and their psychological well-being are closely related to the balance between the resources provided in the work environment and the demands they face. Therefore, providing sufficient resources in the workplace and appropriately managing job demands plays a significant role in reducing employees' intentions to leave their jobs and increasing their subjective well-being. Furthermore, with respect to the impact of subjective well-being on turnover intentions, the results indicate that as individuals' subjective well-being rises, employees' turnover intention declines. For example, a study carried out by Li and colleagues (2025) on nurses revealed that turnover intention was inversely associated with subjective well-being. However, a separate study conducted by Özçelik and Özkoç (2019) found that subjective well-being had a positive influence on employees' turnover intentions. Indeed, research in the literature that directly and thoroughly examines the impact of subjective well-being on turnover intentions remains relatively scarce. While the present study shows similarities with the study by Li et al., it differs from the findings reported by Özçelik and Özkoç.

8. Conclusion

In summary, this study found that: firstly, work demands and work resources are positively related to and positively influence subjective well-being; secondly, work demands and work resources are negatively related to and reduce turnover intention; and finally, employees' subjective well-being negatively affects their turnover intention. Based on these findings, it can be said that work demands and resources, which express the qualities related to the duties and responsibilities of the jobs performed by employees, significantly affect the subjective well-being levels of employees, both in their work lives and in their general lives; in other words, they significantly

influence their perception of happiness throughout their lives. Furthermore, considering the extent to which job demands and resources are met in the job environment, as well as employees' subjective well-being, it is concluded that employees may tend to develop an intention to either remain in the organization or leave their jobs. These findings will both improve employee well-being, health, and motivation in the workplace, and provide employers and managers with valuable information about job demands and resources, employee subjective well-being, and turnover intentions. Furthermore, the research findings provide insights into the measures and changes that managers should take in the work environment. Therefore, this study more clearly reveals the needs of employees in organizations regarding their work environment from the perspective of organizational behavior.

Limitations encountered during research may include studies being restricted to a single sector or region. Examining the same variables across different sectors or with different variables could contribute more significantly to the literature. For example, the way work is carried out, its management, and the needs of the workforce—that is, job demands and resources—may differ between a manufacturing sector and a service sector. Therefore, research conducted across sectors can yield more diverse results and information, making significant contributions to the literature.

Author Contribution Statement

The authors contributed equally to this study.

Ethical Statement

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Social and Human Sciences Ethics Committee of Sivas Cumhuriyet University (Approval No.: E-99711239-050-04-518679, Date: 21.01.2025).

Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and the data were collected in accordance with confidentiality principles.

Financial Support

This research received no financial support.

References

- Ahmad, B., Shahid, M., Huma, Z. E., & Haider, S. (2012). Turnover intention: An HRM Issue in Textile Sector. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 3(12), 125-130.
- Almalki, M.J., FitzGerald, G. & Clark, M. (2012). The Relationship Between Quality of Work-Life and Turnover Intention of Primary Health Care Nurses in Saudi Arabia, *BMC Health Services Research Journal*, 12,1-11.
- Aydogdu S. & Asikgil B. (2011). An empirical study of the relati-

The Effects of Job Demands and Job Resources on Subjective Well-Being and Turnover Intention

- onship among job satisfaction, organizational commitment and turnover intention. *Int Rev Manag Mark*, 1(3), 43–53.
- Bakker, A. B., Hakanen, J. J., Demerouti, E., & Xanthopoulou, D. (2007). Job resources boost work engagement, particularly when job demands are high. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 99(2), 274–284.
- Bakker, A. B., Van Veldhoven, M., & Xanthopoulou, D. (2010). Beyond the demand-control model: Thriving on high job demands and resources. *Journal of Personnel Psychology*, 9(1), 3–16.
- Bakker, A. B. & Demerouti, E. (2014). *Work and wellbeing: wellbeing: a complete reference guide, Volume III*. Edited by Peter Y. Chen and Cary L. Cooper. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. Published.
- Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., Boer, B. & Schaufeli, W. B. (2003). Job Demands and Job Resources as Predictors of Absence Duration and Frequency, *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 62, 341-356.
- Bayram, N. (2004). Sosyal bilimlerde SPSS ile veri analizi. (1. Baskı). Bursa: Ezgi Kitabevi.
- Bon, A. T. & Shire, A. M. (2017). The Impact of Job Demands on Employees' Turnover Intentions: A Study on Telecommunication Sector. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7, (5), 406-412.
- Böckermann, P. & Ilmakunnas, P. (2004). Job Disamenities, Job Satisfaction and On the Job Search: Is There A Nexus? NBER Discussion Paper, 36, Florida: National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Cammann, C., Fichman, M., Jenkins, D. & Klesh, J. (1979). Michigan Organizational Assessment Questionnaire. Michigan: University of Michigan, Ann Arbor.
- Cavanaugh, M. A., Boswell, W. R., Roehling, M. V., & Boudreau, J. W. (2000). An Empirical Examination of Self-reported Work Stress among U.S. Managers. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85(1), 65–74.
- Claes S, Vandepitte S, Clays E., ve Annemans L. (2023) How Job Demands and Job Resources Contribute to Our Overall Subjective Well-Being. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1220263.
- Diener, E., & Diener, C. (1996). Most People Are Happy. *Psychological Science*, 7, 181-185.
- Diener, E. (1984). Subjective Well-Being. *Psychological Bulletin*, 95, 542-575.
- Diener, E., Suh, E. M., Lucas, R. E., & Smith, H. L. (1999). Subjective Well-Being: Three Decades of Progress. *Psychological Bulletin*, 125, 276-302.
- Dishon-Berkovits, M., Riva, E., & Lucchini, M. (2024). The Relationship Between Job Demands, Resources and Subjective Well-being: The Role of Work-Family Conflict Across the Life Course. *Current Psychology*, 43(9), 8085-8101.
- Doğan, T., & Sapmaz, F. (2012). Kişiler Arası İlişki Tarzları ve Öznel İyi Oluş. *Türk Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 10(3), 585-602.
- Eriksson, A., Jutengren, G., & Dellve, L. (2021). Job Demands and Functional Resources Moderating Assistant and Registered Nurses' Intention to Leave. *Nursing Open*, 8(2), 870-881.
- Galletta, M., Portoghese, I., ve Battistelli, A. (2011). Intrinsic Motivation, Job Autonomy and Turnover Intention in the Italian Healthcare: The Mediating Role of Affective Commitment. *Journal of Management Research*, 3(2), 1-19.
- Gencer, N., (Çeviren) (2018). Öznel İyi Oluş: Genel Bir Bakış. *Hitit Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 11(3), 2621-2638.
- Gülertekin, S. (2013). Duygu iklimi ve Liderlik Tarzının İşten Ayrılma Niyetine Etkileri: Alanya'daki Turizm İşletmelerine Yönelik Bir Araştırma, Yüksek Lisans Tezi Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Turizm İşletmeciliği Anabilim Dalı, Çanakkale.
- Han, J., Yin, H., & Wang, J. (2020). Examining The Relationships between Job Characteristics, Emotional Regulation and University Teachers' Well-Being: The Mediation of Emotional Regulation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1727–1727.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Tatham, R. L. & Anderson, R. E. (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis*. Upper Saddle 676 River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Hills, P. & Argyle, M. (2002). The Oxford Happiness Questionnaire: A Compact Scale for The Measurement of Psychological Well-Being. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 33, 1073-1082.
- Hoare, C., & Vandenberghe, C. (2024). Are They Created Equal? A Relative Weights Analysis of The Contributions of Job Demands and Resources to Well-Being and Turnover Intention. *Psychological Reports*, 127(1), 392-418.
- Hoonakker, P.L.T., Carayon, P. & Korunka, C. (2013). Using The Job-Demands-Resources Model to Predict Turnover in The Information Technology Workforce – General Effects and Gender Differences. *Horizons of Psychology*, 22, 51–65.
- Hu, L. T. & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff Criteria for Fit Indexes in Covariance Structure Analysis: Conventional Criteria Versus New Alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling :A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(1), 1-55.
- Jasiński, A.V. & Derbis, R. (2022). Work Stressors and Intention to Leave The Current Workplace and Profession: The Mediating Role of Negative Affect At Work. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(21), 1-16.
- Jin, M. H., McDonald, B., & Park, J. (2018). Person–organization Fit and Turnover Intention: Exploring The Mediating Role of Employee Followership and Job Satisfaction Through Conservation of Resources Theory. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 38(2), 167-192.
- Jin, M., Ji, Y., Ding, S., & Wu, X. (2025). The Effects of Dual Job Demands on Primary and Secondary School Teachers' Subjective Well-Being: A Moderated Mediation Model. *Current Psychology*, 44(13), 13154-13166.
- Jones, F. & Fletcher, B. C. (1996). Job Control and Health. In M. J. Schabracq, J. A. M. Winnubst, & C. L. Cooper (Eds.), *Handbook of work and health psychology* (pp. 33–50). Chichester: Wiley.
- Kline, R.B. (2016). *Principles and Practise of Structural Equation Modeling* (4th ed.), NewYork: Guilford Press.
- Kristensen, N., & Westergård-Nielsen, N. (2004). Does Low Job Satisfaction Lead to Job Mobility? IZA Discussion Paper No. 1026.
- Leep-Lazar, K., Ma, C., Dickson, V. V., & Stimpfel, A. W. (2026). Job Demands, Resources, Mental Health, and Intention to Leave Among Early-Career Nurses: A Cross-Sectional Study. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 178, 105396, 1-12.
- LePine, J. A., Podsakoff, N. P., & LePine, M. A. (2005). A Meta-Analytic Test of The Challenge Stressor-Hindrancer Stressor Framework: An Explanation for Inconsistent Relationships Among Stressors and Performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 48(5), 764–775.
- Lesener, T., Gusy, B., & Wolter, C. (2019). The Job Demands-Resources Model: A Meta-Analytic Review of Longitudinal Studies. *Work & Stress*, 33(1), 76-103.
- Li, Y., Zhang, Q., Deng, X., Zhang, J., Li, J., Xia, G., Zhang, J. & Chen, Y.-P. (2025). Relational Job Characteristics and Turnover Intention Among Nurses: The Mediating Role of Subjective Well-Being. *BMC Nursing*, 24(1), 987, 1-10.
- Lin, L. I. N., Siu, O. L., Shi, K., & Bai, X. W. (2009). Challenge and Hindrance Job Demands, Job Resource and Their Relationships with Vigor and Emotional Exhaustion, *International Conference on Management Science & Engineering*, September, 14-16.
- Lykken, D., & Tellegen, A. (1996). Happiness Is A Stochastic Phenomenon, *Psychological Science*, 7(3), 186-189.
- Mansour, S. & Azeem, M.F. (2024). How Do Increased Job Demands Resulting from Rationalization of Costs Exhaust Flight Attendants and Push Them to Leave? An International Study, *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 115, 1-12.
- Metin, B. (2010). *The Antecedents and Consequences of Burnout, Work Engagement and Workaholism*, Master's Thesis, Middle East Technical University, Ankara.
- Molina-Sánchez, H., Ariza-Montes, A., Ortiz-Gómez, M. & Leal-Rodríguez, A. (2019). The Subjective Well-Being Challenge in The Accounting Profession: The Role of Job Resources Horacio. *International Journal of Environmental Research Public Health*, 16, 3073, 1-17.

- Moloney, W., Boxall, P., Parsons, M., & Cheung, G. (2018). Factors Predicting Registered Nurses' Intentions to Leave Their Organization and Profession: A Job Demands-Resources Framework. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 74(4), 864-875.
- Montecinos, C., Allende, C., Valenzuela, J. P., Vanni, X., & Kuzmanic, D. (2026). Chilean Principals' Intention to Leave Their School: A Job Demand and Resource Analysis. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 64(1), 61-76.
- Myers, D.G. & Diener, E. (1995). Who Is Happy? *Psychological Science*, 6(1), 10-19.
- Ostermeier, J., Willem Koops, W. & Peccei, R. (2023). Effects of Job Demands and Resources on The Subjective Well-Being of Teachers. *Review of Educations*, 11(3), 1-19.
- Özçelik Bozkurt, H. & Özkoç, A. G. (2019). Çalışanlarda Öznel İyi Olma Halinin Algılanan İstihdam Edilebilirlik ve İşten Ayrılma Niyeti ile İlişkisi: Konaklama İşletmelerinde Bir Uygulama. *Journal of Tourism and Gastronomy Studies*, 7(1), 265-285.
- Pulido-Martos, M., Cortés-Denia, D., Luque-Reca, O., & Lopez-Zafra, E. (2023). Authentic Leadership and Personal and Job Demands/Resources: A Person-Centered Approach and Links with Work-Related Subjective Well-Being. *Current Psychology*, 42(33), 28994-29011.
- Randhawa, G. (2007). Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intentions : an Empirical Analysis, *Indian Management Studies Journal*, 11, 149-159.
- Rizwan, M., Arshad, M. Q., Munir, H. M. A., Iqbal, F. & Hussain, A. (2014). Determinants of employees intention to leave: A Study from Pakistan, *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 4(3), 1-18.
- Schaufeli, B. & Bakker, A. B. (2004). Job demands, Job Resources, and The Irrelationship with Burnout and Engagement: A Multi-Sample Study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 2(3), 293-315.
- Schaufeli, W. B. (2017). Applying The Job Demands-Resources Model: A 'How to' Guide to Measuring and Tackling Work Engagement and Burnout. *Organizational Dynamics*, 46(2), 120-132.
- Schaufeli, W. B., & Taris, T. W. (2014). A Critical Review of The Job Demands-Resources Model: Implications for Improving Work and Health. In G. F. Bauer & O. Hämmig (Eds.), *Bridging Occupational, Organizational and Public Health: A Transdisciplinary Approach*, 43-68.
- Schermelleh-Engel, K., Moosbrugger, H., & Müller, H. (2003). Evaluating The Fit of Structural Equation Models: Tests of Significance and Descriptive Goodness-of-Fit Measures. *Methods of Psychological Research*, 8(2), 23-74.
- Sutherland, M., ve Wilhelm, J. (2004). Factors Affecting the Retention of Knowledge Workers. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 2(2), 55-64.
- Tabachnick, B. G. & Fidell, L. S. (2015). *Using Multivariate Statistics* (6th ed.). Pearson. (Turkish translation by M. Baloğlu, Nobel Academic Publishing).
- Tadić, M., Bakker, A. B. & Oerlemans, W. G. (2015). Challenge versus hindrance job demands and well-being: A Diary Study on The Moderating Role of Job Resources. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 88(4), 702-725.
- Tummers, L.G. & Bakker, A. B. (2021). Leadership and Job Demands-Resources Theory: A Systematic Review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 1-13.
- Van den Broeck, A., De Cuyper, N., De Witte, H. & Vansteenkiste, M. (2010). Not all Job Demands Are Equal: Differentiating Job Hindrances and Job Challenges in The Job Demands- Resources Model. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 19, 735-759.
- Vigneshwaran, D., & Mohankumar, S. (2022). Intent to Quit: A Literature Review. *Global Multidisciplinary Research & Academic Foundation (GMRAF)*. Chennai https://www.researchgate.net/publication/366596333_Intent_To_Quit_A_Literature_Review [Retrieved June 4, 2024]
- Xanthopoulou, D., Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E. & Schaufeli, W. B. (2007). The Role of Personal Resources in The Job Demands-Resources Model. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 14(2), 121.
- Yapıcı, N. (2008). İş Yerinde Sistematik Yıldıрма (Mobbing), Algılanan Nedenleri ve İş Tatmini ile İşten Ayrılma Niyeti Üzerine Etkisi: Antalya İli Tarım Sektöründe Bir Araştırma. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Akdeniz Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Antalya.
- Yurcu, G. & Atay, H. (2015). Çalışanların Öznel İyi Oluşunu Etkileyen Demografik Faktörlerin İncelenmesi: Antalya İli Konaklama İşletmeleri Örneği, *Manas Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 4(2), 17-33.
- Zhao, P., Yuan, J. & Hu, Y. (2023). Work Hours, Job Resources and Subjective Well Being of Chinese Faculty: An Empirical Analysis Based on a Sequential Mediation Model. *Research in Higher Education*, 65, 965-988.
- https://www.sgk.gov.tr/Istatistik/Yillik/fcd5e-59b-6af9-4d90-a451-ee7500eb1cb4/sosyal_guvenlik_kurumu. [Retrieved December 24, 2025]